

TALENT DEVELOPMENT AND ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS: A STUDY OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Talent development has become a critical strategic priority for organisations seeking sustainable growth and competitive advantage. This paper explores key approaches, methods, and processes of talent development, with a particular focus on educational institutions. Drawing on existing literature, the study examines formal and informal development practices, including training, mentoring, coaching, and job-based learning. It highlights the role of talent development in enhancing employee performance, motivation, and organisational effectiveness. The paper also analyses the importance of training needs assessment as integral components of talent management. Based on the findings, practical recommendations are provided to strengthen talent development systems in educational settings. The study concludes that a well-designed talent development strategy significantly contributes to institutional success, improved teaching quality, and long-term organisational sustainability.

Introduction

In the modern knowledge-driven economy, talent is widely recognised as one of the most valuable organisational assets. Organisations increasingly rely on highly skilled and adaptable employees to maintain competitiveness and achieve strategic objectives. As a result, talent development has emerged as a central component of human resource management, focusing not only on attracting talented individuals but also on nurturing, retaining, and maximising their potential.

Talent development encompasses a wide range of practices, including formal training programs, mentoring and coaching relationships, and experiential learning opportunities such as job rotations and project assignments. These approaches enable employees to enhance their competencies, adapt to changing organisational demands, and contribute more effectively to performance outcomes. Furthermore, talent development plays a crucial role in fostering employee engagement, job satisfaction, and long-term commitment.

In the context of educational institutions, the importance of talent development is even more pronounced. Academic staff directly influence the quality of teaching, student satisfaction, and institutional reputation. Therefore, investing in their professional growth is essential for maintaining high standards of education and achieving competitive positioning in the sector. This paper aims to explore the key methods and processes of talent development and to evaluate their impact on organisational success, particularly within educational environments.

Talent development approach, methods and processes

Talent is one of the main company benefits in the market. Talents are expensive and difficult to replace therefore attraction, development and retention process of the talents should be one of the main goals of the successfully growing organisation (Mehdiabadi and Li, 2016). Pruis (2011) pointed out that talent development (TD) helps organisation to achieve business strategy, competitive advantage and revenue, and also TD increases staff motivation and self-organization. Talent development is a crucial indicator of organizational success, Tavis (2008) described in his research TD as a talent strategy, acquisition, long term development, engagement and retention, while Ibeh and Debrah (2011) identified talent development as a coaching, feedback, review process, training and mentoring. As it was concluded by Chandler et al. (2010) mentoring and coaching are relatively at a cheap rate, however they increase employees job satisfaction and performance, organizational commitment and trust (Mercurio, 2015). It was identified four elements of TD programs by Garavan et al. (2012) they are: (1) formal training, (2) mentoring and coaching, (3) job-based learning experiences through job rotations and (4) informal/incidental learning opportunities.

McCauley et al. (2010) in his paper described three main categories of talent development methods:

- Developmental relationships. Relationship is strong tool of learning and development process because it helps to build support and challenge (McCauley and Douglas, 2004). One of the popular examples of developmental relationships is mentoring and coaching.
- Developmental assignments. This method focuses on learning by doing, working on problems, challenging assignments and dilemmas. McCauley et al. (2010) emphasized job rotations, project assignments and transfers as examples of developmental assignments method.
- Formal programs include corporate and education programs and trainings that help employees to improve their professional competence and job performance.

Relatively close results were founded out by Manon Ruijters (2006) cited by Pruis (2011). She concluded her research with the findings that talents usually preferred 2 modes of learning: observing and learning by doing.

The table below outlines the talent development process and its components as well as it shows tie with organizational success.

of

Model
Talent

Development. Source (Panda and Sahoo, 2015)

Although talent development has more positive aspects for the organization, its implementation can be followed with some difficulties such as to define who needs to develop and what competencies to focus on, identify and select qualified trainers, coaches and mentors within organisation (Garavan et al., 2012).

Talent development in educational institutions

According to Hazelkorn (2017) and Lynch (2015) talent helps to raise profit of the educational organisation, boost its competitive and ranking, as well as increase productivity and performance. Talent of educational institution influences on the new student attraction and providing high-quality teaching and learning process (Hazelkorn, 2017). According to Kamal (2017) talent development process is crucial for long-term successful growth and development of the organisation. Hatum (2010) in his research highlighted that “high-performing organisations are identifiable by their talented individuals who are able to show initiative, creativity and excellence in performance and productivity”. Based on Prinsloo (2017) the main factor of talent development is training and mentoring programs including learning and teaching courses that allow academic staff to gain update knowledge and skills. It is crucial for educational institution to provide professional learning and growth opportunities for academic staff in order to increase motivation (Photanan, 2004; Lynn, 2002). Leslie (1989) highlighted that professional growth is essential tool of teachers motivator and career development. It was also found out that coaching talent is a key process of talent development in education institution. It includes development, learning and teaching process, training and mentoring (AlKerdawy, 2016; Lyria, 2014). It was concluded by Tatoglu et al. (2016) and Ford (2017) that talent development is crucial for educational institution because it helps to achieve strategic goals, meet main requirements and form the foundation to implement business strategy.

Finally, for success and development of institutional education it is important to attract, develop and retain the talent. Number of research in education sphere concluded with importance of development of strategies for improving employees' performance including competencies, motivation development and increasing of career development (AlKerdawy, 2016; Lyria 2014).

Recommendations

In order to develop organizational efficiency, performance outcomes and quality service organisation should invest in promoting a learning culture. Talent strategy helps to feel certain that the appropriate knowledge and skills are available to deliver the best work outcomes (Thunnissen et al., 2013). It was concluded by Tatoglu et al. (2016) and Ford (2017) that talent development is crucial for educational institution because it helps to achieve strategic goals, meet main requirements and form the foundation to implement business strategy.

Training needs analysis

Training needs analysis is important tool for understanding needs of employees as well as evaluating company goals. Needs analysis should be done before trainings are arranged, it will show starting point and goals for achievement. Analysis is crucial for development of effective training materials and effective use of time.

Types of training needs analyses:

- Knowledge – knowledge that are required for the specific area of the work; easy to identify
- Skills – both practical and soft skills; moderately difficult to identify
- Abilities – independence of the employee, ability to make decisions and be goal-oriented; most difficult to identify.

Levels of need analysis:

- Organisational (policy for training, achieving company's goals, strategies and objectives)
- Job (understanding the main responsibilities and required skill)
- Individual (identify employees who need the development, their level of current knowledge in the area, learning style).

Training needs analysis methods:

- Questionnaires
- Observation
- Interviews
- Examining work
- Assessments / Tests
- Competitive analysis

It is recommended to use observation and work examining method, because they are one of the best practice to assess teachers' work and organize required trainings. Assessment method can be used in order to evaluate employee knowledge and whether the training is required in this particular area. Assessment can be as a short multiple-choice and can be conducted online for easier analyses process. Competitive analysis is also powerful tool, it helps to understand where the company stands in the industry. Successful practices and model can be adopted for the education organisation.

Training

Based on research done from literature review talent development is highly important for educational institution as from profit point of view as well as from ranking, customer attraction that is influenced by high-quality learning environment. As it was observed one of the main factors of TD

is training programs including learning and teaching courses that allow academic staff to gain update knowledge.

– The educational institution should analyze the training need, namely collect information about required area of improvement, audience, module on the training, timeframe etc.

– Based on research it was found out that coaching method is a main process of talent development in education institution. It includes development, learning and teaching process, training and mentoring (AlKerdawy, 2016; Lyria, 2014). The main aim of peer observation is to advance teaching practice through feedback that is focused on developing student learning process.

Strategy of recruiting talents from an external market is not enough, in order to be successful company should also focus on the internal development of the employees. The organisation might gain from investing on training by: decreasing in turnover rate and cost of recruitment; increasing in motivation and performance management; more efficiency and less errors; advancing of service quality, reputation and ranking.

Conclusion

In conclusion, talent development represents a fundamental driver of organisational performance and long-term success, particularly within educational institutions where human capital plays a decisive role. The findings of this study demonstrate that effective talent development strategies – combining formal training, mentoring, coaching, and experiential learning – significantly enhance employee competencies, motivation, and overall performance.

The analysis also highlights the importance of structured processes such as training needs assessment in ensuring that development initiatives are aligned with organisational goals and individual requirements. While implementing talent development systems may present certain challenges, including identifying development priorities and sourcing qualified mentors, these obstacles can be addressed through strategic planning and a strong commitment to a learning-oriented culture.

Ultimately, organisations that invest in continuous professional development and create opportunities for career growth are more likely to retain talented employees, improve service quality, and strengthen their competitive position. For educational institutions, in particular, a comprehensive approach to talent development not only enhances staff performance but also contributes to improved student outcomes and institutional reputation.

Bibliography:

1. AlKerdawy, M.M.A. (2016), "The relationship between human resource management ambidexterity and talent management: the moderating role of electronic human resource management", *International Business Research*, Vol. 9 No. 6.
2. Chandler, D.E., Hall, D.T. and Kram, K.E. (2010), "A developmental network & relational savvy approach to talent development: a low-cost alternative", *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 39 No. 1.
3. Ford, D.G. (2017), "Talent management and its relationship to successful veteran transition into the civilian workplace: practical integration strategies for the HRD professional", *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, Vol. 19 No. 1.
4. Garavan, T.N., Carbery, R., Rock, A., Garavan, T.N., Carbery, R. and Rock, A. (2012), "Mapping talent development: definition, scope and architecture", *European Journal of Training and Development*, Vol. 36 No. 1.
5. Hatum, A. (2010), *Next Generation Talent Management: Talent Management to Survive Turmoil*, 1st ed., Palgrave Macmillan, Hampshire.

6.

- Hazelkorn, E. (2017), *Rankings and Higher Education: Reframing Relationships within and between States*, Centre for Global Higher Education, UCL Institute of Education, London, available at: www.researchcghe.org/ (accessed 15 December 2020).
7. Ibeh, K. and Debrah, Y.A. (2011), "Female talent development and African business schools", *Journal of World Business*, Vol. 46 No. 1.
 8. Kamal, M. (2017), "Challenges in talent management in selected public universities", *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, Vol. 3 No. 5.
 9. Leslie, K. (1989), "Administrators must consider and improve teacher satisfaction", *NASSP Bulletin*, Vol. 73 No. 1.
 10. Lynch, K. (2015), "Control by numbers: new managerialism and ranking in higher education", *Critical Studies in Education*, Vol. 56 No. 2.
 11. Lynn, S. (2002), "The winding pathy: understanding the career cycle of teachers", *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, Vol. 75 No. 4.
 12. Lyria, R.K. (2014), "Effect of talent management on organizational performance in companies listed in Nairobi securities exchange in Kenya", doctor of philosophy (Human Resource Management)
 13. McCauley, C. and Douglas, C. (2004), "Developmental relationships", in McCauley, C. and Velsor, E (Eds), *The Center for Creative Leadership Handbook Leadership Development*, 2nd ed., Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, CA.
 14. McCauley, C., Kanaga, K. and Lafferty, K. (2010), "Leader development systems", in Van Velsor, McCauley, C. and Ruderman, M. (Eds), *The Center for Creative Leadership: Handbook of Leadership Development*, 3rd ed., San Francisco, Jossey-Bass, CA.
 15. Mehdiabadi, H.A. and Li, J. (2016), "Understanding talent development and implications for human resource development: an integrative literature review", *Human Resource Development Review*, Vol. 15 No. 3.
 16. Mercurio, Z.A. (2015), "Affective commitment as a core essence of organizational commitment: an integrative literature review", *Human Resource Development Review*, Vol. 14 No. 4.
 17. Panda, S. and Sahoo, C.K. (2015). Strategic talent development interventions: an analysis. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 47 (1), 15–22. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1108/ict-05-2014-0031>.
 18. Photanan, T. (2004), *Human Resource Focus*, Innographics Ltd, Bangkok.
 19. Prinsloo, H. (2017), "How South African businesses design and execute transformation initiatives: Implications for coaching", master of business executive coaching thesis, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg.
 20. Pruis, E. (2011). The five key principles for talent development. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 43 (4), 206–216. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1108/00197851111137825>.
 21. Tatoglu, E., Glaister, A.J. and Demirbag, M. (2016), "Talent management motives and practices in an emerging market: a comparison between MNEs and local firms", *Journal of World Business*, Vol. 51 No. 2.
 22. Tavis, A. (2008), "Leading the talent development life cycle", *People & Strategy*, Vol. 31 No. 1.
 23. Thunnissen, M., Boselie, P. and Fruytier, B. (2013), "A review of talent management: infancy or adolescence?", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 24 No. 9.